

A consolidated ethics protocol for HTS work in a multi-Omic era

We produced ethics application templates to serve as clear, participant-focused blueprints for researchers at the University of Malta. The Information Sheets were drafted in straightforward language to explain the study's aims, procedures and data-management rights, then translated into both English and Maltese to ensure accessibility for all local participants. We used templates that were previously developed by the DwarnaBio biobank (University of Malta Biobank), and which we have amended for general use by researchers at the University of Malta.

The documents produced are:

Participant Consent Forms (English and Maltese)

Participant Questionnaire (English and Maltese)

Project Information Booklet (English and Maltese)

The documents are deposited at [doi:10.5281/zenodo.16599157](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16599157)